

THE WORD CHOICE FROM SYNONYMIC RANGE IN MEDIA CONTEXT

Jumaniyazova Shahlo Zohid kizi¹,
Saparbayeva Gulandam Masharipovna²

¹Year 3 student of Foreign language and literature department,
Foreign Philology faculty, Urgench State University

²Supervisor: PhD., PhD in Philological science, Translation
theory and practice department, Urgench State university

E-mail: saparbaevagulandom@rambler.ru

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the importance of word choice from the range of synonyms in media texts. The semantic nature of words is analyzed as the key factors of creation of media texts. The choice of words for publicist style is studied from the point of view of linguistics.

Synonymy is a linguistic feature that include different language units with the same or similar meaning. The word synonymy is derived from Greek word 'synonymos' that means a word with the 'same name'. The word, word-combinations, phrases and syntactic structures are called as synonyms as they comprise a general meaning (with the same denotative meaning), supplementary (connotative) meaning to define expressive, stylistic and other semantic relations among words within a sentence. For instance, the following words are used synonymously in a text: again, over, once more, yet again, over again, another time, all over again.

Depending on what kind of language features, the phenomenon of synonymy is divided into lexical, phraseological, and syntactic groups. The group of words with similar meanings is called synonyms. The

range of synonyms include two or more words. For instance, the following range of synonyms can be of nine words and they are composed of several more words. There can be one or more synonyms with similar meanings. E.g., The word finish can be synonym with leave, graduate, end in one meaning and it can be synonym with loose, die, abolish, expire, complete, close in another meaning.

The main word is a word in the range of synonyms that can comprise all meanings of others. The main word belongs to the current literary language and it can be differentiated without emotional color, neutrality according to the style of the context. It differs from other words in the range by its characteristics and is widely used in the language compared to others according to these semantic features. For instance, in the range of synonymy these words are similar in meaning: amazing,

astonishing, surprising, shocking, astonishing, bewildering, beyond belief, the word amazing is considered the main word. Other words are differentiated from each other with their own content: the word amazing expresses a most impressive degree; while the words astonishing, surprising, have a more bookish style, astonishing, bewildering, beyond belief are used relatively less often. It is important to use the words correctly according to their own characteristics and usage in the context media.

Nowadays many scientists admit to distinguish between the linguistic meaning of a word and the pragmatic meaning of the concept denoted by the word. Both linguistic meaning and concept are the categories of thought. Both of them represent the reflections of the outer world in speaker's mind. However, these are different types of reflections. If the concept is the complete reflection of a particular category of objects and events, linguistic meaning only defines their specific features.

However, it should not be assumed that all the words in a language unite on basis of subjective logical connection. Although this is correct from a subjective logical point of view, given the lexical and grammatical connection, in many cases, it is not accepted in a media language or compound structure according to the demands of press. Thus, according to a specific word form or syntactic function it can be limited with the language system if the lexical and grammatical conformity of words to the text is relatively free and subject logically limited, but quite broader, lexical and grammatical context. For this reason, the recent volumes of dictionaries are

published in the form of specialized or large scale encyclopedic dictionaries.

Enough attention is paid to showing the syntagmatic relations of the word in modern dictionaries. For example, in the "New Explanatory Dictionary of Synonyms" (Y.D. Apresyan), although in fact they are distinguished by their correspondence with each other, in the description of the meaning of each synonymous word, the lexical conformity is analyzed in details and impossible compounds. Example: the words home and denote a building for human habitation especially one that consists of a ground floor and one or more upper stores. According to this dictionary definition, home is related to family, motherland, country, life, traditions, so the definitions are suitable only with the words mother-hood, family. While the word-combination to build home/house may denote completely different concepts in media text. To build home means to have family and live in a certain place forever, and the combination to build house means to construct the parts of the house it can be bedroom, living-room, kitchen, swimming pool, pavement and etc. Moreover, the lexical and grammatical correspondence can be included into a specific form of the dictionary.

When thinking about the concept of correspondence with the text, choosing a word from the list of synonyms is closely related to the concept of context, as well as the norm of the context, its type and the place of the word in the context. Because syntagmatic relations are based on positional relations and not oppositional (like paradigmatic) relations.

It is known that the context is the communicative situation or the semantic part of the text, which helps to clearly

identify the meaning of each word included in it. In a broad sense, context is also the conditions of using a certain linguistic unit in a language in use and speech act situation.

Distinguishing the concepts used in mass media and press requires taking into account the possibilities of a narrow context (= a phrase or an idiom) and a broad context that can be a predicative construction of a simple or compound sentences, passages, paragraphs, and texts of brief news items, advertisements, public articles, announcement and etc. The concept also has an additional context - this is the context of an entire work or even an epoch, for example, the meaning of the title of Goncharov's novel *Qiya* can be understood only from the context of the entire work, and the title of Herzen's journal *The Call* only in the context of the time, under the context norm, its sufficiency is assumed to understand the meaning of the word that means to understand the specific meaning of the word included in the context. Often, a simple phrase is enough to understand the meaning of the phrases wash the floor of the house, to build a house, to house an orphan. But sometimes one phrase is not enough, because there may be ambiguity in understanding the phrase as to buy a house may mean to buy an area for a house, a place of an accommodation, a flat, the building. In this case the user needs to refer to the wider context: to buy land for a house, to buy a shelter to live with accommodation, to buy an apartment in a block of houses, to buy a building to live in with family.

In cases where the implementation of the meaning is carried out under conditions of limited compatibility, the context is called permanent (consequences, as a result will be ...), but this has already become an object of study in the field of phraseology. Thus, a word in a context acquires a certain meaning in relation to other words of the context in a given position.

The meaning manifests itself fully in the supported position of the main features of the word the meaning and it is chosen as the strongest component in the synonymy range, which is the most suitable for the requirement of the context. For example, in the combinations of daily news, day-to-day news, everyday news, several adjectives were made with the word news by choosing the most appropriate component that expresses a new meaning. The main components of the synonymic range, which are not selected for this context, are called weak positional components, because they generate uncertainty in the content of the text. For instance, the combinations with other components of synonymic range such as regular news, quotidian news, circadian news are almost never found in the media context.

As a conclusion to the point it is appropriate to consider mass media and press in the syntagmatic level of language studies taking into consideration the contextual meaning of specific words common in media context. In this case, synonymous words and expressions are studied as a unit of the lexical syntagmatic system as a research element that serve as the main feature in providing the peculiarity of the media language.

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